

RADIANT GOURMET Event

**Underutilised Crops
new-products, -value chains,
and -relationships.**

Networking with sister projects and socioeconomists

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Executive Summary

RADIANTs 1st GOURMET event was integrated into the project first General Assembly (GA), which took place in parallel with the [BioValue](#) project GA; and as part of the 182nd meeting of the European Association of Agricultural Economists (EAAE).

The GOURMET event celebrated underutilised crops (UC) that are being used to develop exciting new products and value chains. As such, it provided an opportunity for RADIANT AURORAs (farm-based pilot studies) to showcase their UCs, UC-products, and share their experiences regarding their value chains and business models with other RADIANT partners; partners of the sister projects ([Crop Diva, Bio Value, and DivinFood](#)), and other stakeholders attending the EAAE congress.

RADIANT AURORA FARMS shared their success stories and challenges in UCs valorisation via living-poster presentations. The event also incorporated a GOURMET Showcase, where AURORA farms displayed their UC-products and provide all participants the chance to interact more personally and directly sharing their experience, and tasting UC-based products.

The event encouraged building of the UC community, and demonstrated how UC can be used to successfully develop novel and dynamic value chains.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background & Objectives

RADIANT is 4-year research project funded by the European Commission's under the Horizon 2020 programme. This project aims to:

1. release the value of Underutilised Crops (UCs) and enable a transformation towards sustainable 'Dynamic Value Chains' (or, "DVCs") that foster greater levels of agrobiodiversity, and;
2. identify solutions to achieve more successful cultivation of UCs, and their integration into profitable and resilient value chains.

To help deliver these, RADIANT selected a suite of 20 Pilot Studies called "AURORAs" (farms, and ex farm gate businesses) from across the different biogeographical regions in Europe (Atlantic/Boreal; Mediterranean; Continental), where the inclusion of agrobiodiversity via UCs is being done in an exemplar way; including capitalising on native crop biodiversity. In these AURORAs, DVCs are implemented well using new marketing channels that enhance consumer-producer links.

Within RADIANT, a series of three GOURMET events are planned punctuated throughout the project's life cycle, to provide an opportunity for AURORA Leaders to share their experience regarding their value chains and business models, and to showcase their UCs and UC-based products.

RADIANT's 1st GOURMET event took after its General Assembly (GA) meeting on September 13th 2022 in Crete, and focussed on '*Promoting Agrobiodiversity*'; and '*the role of agrobiodiversity on enabling resilient in value chains*'.

1.2 Event Framework

This GOURMET event had a series of Living Poster presentations by the RADIANT) AURORAs (farm/value chain-based) partners and was attended by representatives of RADIANT's three sister projects ([Crop Diva](#), [Bio Value](#), and [DivinFood](#)), who also presented their projects. This interaction allowed the partners from the projects to discuss commonality, differences, and opportunity for collaboration.

One of the sister projects ([BioValue](#)) organised the parallel event: **182nd European Association of Agricultural Economists (EAAE) EAAE Seminar** (<http://182eaae.maich.gr/>), 'Sustainability via Biodiverse Agri-Food Value Chains' (14th – 15th September); which also saw the participation of several RADIANT partners with presentations, and chairing the session, 'Farmers perceptions and attitudes regarding biodiverse production systems' by RADIANT Coordinator Marta Vasconcelos (and Deputy Coordinator Pietro Iannetta).

The GOURMET event also included a 'Gourmet Showcase' that provided an opportunity for RADIANT AURORA farmers, to further share their experiences and showcase their UC products.

2. Presentations

2.1 Participation in the 182nd EAAE Seminar

Several RADIANT partners participated with presentations and posters in the 182nd EAAE Seminar “Sustainability via Biodiverse Agri-Food Value Chains” organised by BioValue, which took place in parallel with GOURMET Event.

Figure 1. Poster session dedicated to RADIANT project in 182nd EAAE seminar.

Figure 2. Session chaired by RADIANT coordinator (Marta Vasconcelos) at the 182nd EAAE seminar.

2.2 Poster Presentations (GOURMET Event)

The 1st GOURMET event also provided a good opportunity for the RADIANT AURORA farms to present their work through a series of posters and share their UC-journey and perspective with a broad range of stakeholders including partners from the sister projects. These posters have been uploaded to the RADIANT website ([Aurora Farms – Radiant Project](#)), and were as follows (see [Appendix I](#) for definition of partner acronyms):

1. UoN - Luis C Salazar-Licea, Guillermina Mendiondo, Sean Mayes – ["Tropical UCs: Bambara groundnut, Foxtail millet, Winged"](#).
2. ESSRG - Katalin Réthy, Alexandra Czeglédi - ["Szezon Kert"](#)
3. CSIC- Diego Rubiales, M.J. Cobos, A.M. Villegas - ["Legume \(and others\) cultivars more adapted and productive"](#).
4. AUA - Georgia Ntatsi, Ioannis Karavidas, Orfeas Voutsinos-Frantzis, Theodora Ntanasi, Dimitrios Savvas - ["Innovative ecofriendly management practices for sustainable production of underutilised leafy greens \(ULGs\)"](#).
5. UNITO - Francesca Cardinale, Ivan Visentin, Andrea Schubert - ["Stress-resilient tomato landraces as a tool to increase farming sustainability in challenging conditions"](#).
6. CUT - Gholamreza Gohari, Georgia Ntatsi, Vasileios Fotopoulos - ["Seed priming of Sonchus oleraceus with Melatonin enriched Chitosan nanoparticles \(CTS-Mel NPs\) as a new priming agent"](#)
7. CRPA - Paolo Mantovi, Elena Bortolazzo - ["Edible Park"](#)
8. UL - Maurice Deasy, David Styles - ["CANVAS: heritage variety beer via direct marketing"](#)
9. JHI - Timothy S George, Joanne Russell, Pietro Iannetta and Fanny Tran - ["Bere barley"](#).
10. UNIVPM – Chiara Santamarina, Laura Nanni, Roberto Papa - ["Improving maize/bean intercropping through participatory plant breeding"](#)
11. ILU - Lina Krenz, Daniel Pleissner - ["Utilization of grass and faba beans"](#)
12. FDM – Alfredo Sendim, Ana Fonseca, Ana Vasconcelos - ["Improving agroecological production of Sweet Acorn and Jujube in Alentejo"](#).
13. UNISG – Paola Migliorini and Chiara Bassignana - ["Wheat local varieties of Piedmont, Italy"](#)
14. CONAT - ["Recovery and revalorization of traditional fruit tree varieties from the Castellón region \(Spain\)"](#).

15. HIW - Anna Trettenero, Mauro Grandi - "High Protein Pea on Conservation Agriculture to be processed into high value, food grade, functional proteins, TVPs and by-products".
16. DIKOT - Dr Maria Boile, George Lyras - """Dikotylon"" Legumes of Fe-neos".
17. IAI - B. Bojinov, H. Tzvetanov, S. Vasileva, S. Boyanova - "IAI - Chemapool collaboration".
18. CRPA - Elena Bortolazzo, Maria Teresa Pacchioli, Paolo Mantovi, Fabrizio Ruozi, Roberto Davolio - "Local alfalfa ecotypes and underutilised legumes for animal feeding in the Apennine area (Italy)".

Figure 3. AURORA FARMs posters and UC products showcase. Left) example of a poster prepared by HiWeiss AURORA farm; right) photos of participants discussing the posters.

3. Gourmet Showcase

3.1. RADIANT AURORA Showcase

This event also provided an excellent opportunity for the RADIANT AURORA Farms to showcase their products. For the full list, see **Table 1** below.

Table 1. List of UC products showcased by the RADIANT AURORAs Farms.

Partner	Name of Product	Type	UC used	Brief Description
JHI	Nadar Gin	Product	Peas	These products originally emerged from the EU-project TRUE and are showcased here as they are highly relevant to RADIANT, with an evolving dynamic value chain. Peas are underutilised across the UK and are grown on less than 1% of arable land in Scotland. Peas have been developed using novel processes for distilling in a short value chain to yield a climate positive neutral spirit, and high protein co-products for animal feed.
JHI	Nadar Vodka	Product	Peas	
UL	CANVAS beer	Product	Hunter heritage barley	CANVAS brewery is a microbrewery based on a farm, that uses local ingredients and direct marketing. They have experience growing 'Hunter' spring barley variety alongside commercial malting barley varieties. This heritage barley has exhibited lower yield but higher perceived flavour, and increased resistance to Fusarium. CANVAS brewery is keen to understand prospective benefits of grain-legume intercropping and organic. The beer is produced & packaged on farm using traditional methods and renewable energy. Approximately half of beer produced is delivered directly to consumers, but there are challenges for scaling this model up, e.g., high investment costs for malting equipment, and distribution logistics.
FDM	Acorn Biscuits	Product	Acorn - Holm oaks	These were the first products developed by FDM based on acorns in 2008. The acorns were produced in a man-made silvo-pastoral system called Montado. This sustainable food production system allowed a set of products including cork, meat, acorns, honey, hunting, mushrooms and provides ecosystem services as biodiversity, regulation of the hydric system, carbon fixation, cultural heritage, and touristic services.
FDM	Acorn Infusion			
FDM	Acorn flour			
FDM	Fermented acorns			
FDM	Jujube date	Product		These products are available in Alentejo gardens and used to be sold as snacks in

Partner	Name of Product	Type	UC used	Brief Description
FDM	Fresh ju-jube		Jujube - Ziziphus ju-juba	the 1970's. It is very resistant to drought and has medicinal and important nutritional functions.
HIW	Egg-less gluten free cookies	Product	yellow pea	Cookies made with HiWeiss with Pea protein used as substitute for eggs to allow the aggregation of corn and buckwheat gluten free flours. The product can also be suitable for vegans when margarine is used.
HIW	Egg-less Choc chunk cookies	Product	yellow pea	Cookies made with HiWeiss with Pea protein used as substitute of eggs. The product can be suitable for vegans when margarine is used as a source of fat.
SB	High-protein rye mix bread	Product	pea, chick-pea	A blend of legume proteins for a high-protein bread based on wheat-rye flour mix.
SB	Small baked goods with minor cereals	Product	pea, chick-pea	High-protein small baked goods on spelt-flour base.
SB	Yeas-free small baked goods	Product	chickpea	Yeast-free, high-protein small baked goods on wholemeal spelt-wheat flour mix.
SB	Wellness bread	Product	chickpea	Wheat-rye mix bread, with different oily seeds.
Dikotylon	Fava of Feneos	Product	fava beans	Designated as a PDO/PGI product, "Fava Feneou" is highly nutritious product

Figure 4. Photos of UC-based products showcased at the Gourmet event. From left to right: “Fava Feneou” product by DIKOT; Cookies by HiWeiss with Pea protein; Nadar Vodka and Nadar Gin by JHI; Egg-less Choc chunk cookies by HiWeiss; “Wellness Bread” by SB; Acorn Cookies (FdM).

4. Panel Discussion

At the EAAE-based GOURMET event, the UC-based products showcased spanned food, feed or non-food prototypes - to demonstrate the range of products that could be produced from UCs. Discussion was “open” around the poster session and UC-products showcase.

The discussion focused on the following specific questions:

- *What are the best UCs to ensure the resilience of European agrifood systems in your biogeography; and why?*
- *Should there be a compromise between ecosystem services and productivity; can they go hand-in-hand?*
- *What value chains are being/have been mostly disrupted in your region due to uncertainty events (war, pandemics, etc)?*
- *Are governments responding appropriately to the value chain disruptions in your country, namely considering the safeguarding of the agroecological principles?*

This discussion around the AURORA FARMS posters and their products was extremely positive, having helped the AURORA partners to team building within the RADIANT project, RADIANT sister projects, and EAAE congress delegates.

5. Concluding Remarks

RADIANT's 1st Gourmet Event played an important role in raising awareness among RADIANT partners and other key stakeholders of the AURORAs integrated into the project. This initial gathering not only highlighted the significance of these farms and ex-farm gate Pilot Studies, but also showcased the potential of their contributions to the broader goals of the UCs promotion. Furthermore, the event provided an invaluable opportunity for participants to engage with UC-products, offering a unique sensory experience as they were able to taste and learn about the UCs innovative products, and their respective value chains. The hands-on interaction with these products emphasised the importance of sustainability, local sourcing, and innovation in agriculture.

The event facilitated meaningful dialogue among partners from all four projects, fostering an open exchange of ideas about common goals, differing approaches, and potential avenues for collaboration. The discussions found several opportunities for strengthening synergies across the projects, allowing stakeholders to compare strategies, share best practices, and identify areas where combined efforts could maximize impact.

As the event ended, a discussion emerged regarding the future GOURMET events. It was proposed that future event be held at a RADIANT partner institution, thereby allowing for a more diverse representation of stakeholders. The inclusion of a broader range of stallholders beyond the AURORAs would enhance the variety and depth of products showcased, further enriching the collaborative environment and expanding the reach of the UCs valorisation. This would not only elevate the profile of future events but also deepen the engagement between partners, local stakeholders, and the wider community.

Appendix I

RADIANT Project partners defined by: their role in RADIANT, short name, country, and partner type. RTD = Research and technology Development; SME = Small or Medium-sized Enterprise, NGO = Non-Governmental Organisation.

No	Participant organisation name [main role in RADIANT]	Short name	Country	Type
1	UNIVERSIDADE CATÓLICA PORTUGUESA [Coordination]	UCP	Portugal	RTD
2	INOVAČIJSKO TEHNOLOSKI GROZD MURSKA SOBOTA [Mapping VC actors, Block chain implementation, DIH AGRIFOOD]	ITC	Slovenia	SME
3	CREATIVE MINDS [Project branding, digital marketing capacitation]	CM	Portugal	SME
4	CROPS FOR THE FUTURE [Breeding, CropBASE-EU /CropStore] [AURORA Farm]	CFF	UK	NGO
5	ENVIRONMENTAL SOCIAL SCIENCES RESEARCH GROUP [Transformative policies for dynamic value chains, 2 AURORA Farms]	ESSRG	Hungary	SME
6	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR INV CIENTIFICAS [Breeding, agronomy, AURORA Farm]	CSIC	Spain	RTD
7	GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON [AURORA Farm]	AUA	Greece	RTD
8	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO [Biofertilizers, AURORA FARM]	UNITO	Italy	Higher Education
9	DEUTSCHES INSTITUT FÜR LEBENSMITTELTECHNIK EV [Novel foods, small batch processing modules, RADIANT LCA]	DIL	Germany	RTD
10	UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK [RADIANT-Metrics, multi-attributes LCA for new labelling framework, AURORA FARM]	UL	Ireland	Higher Education
11	TRINITY COLLEGE DUBLIN [RADIANT-Metrics, multi-attributes LCA for new labelling framework]	TCD	Ireland	Higher Education
12	THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE [CREATOR and GOURMET events, social sciences, rural economics, AURORA Farm]	JHI	UK	RTD
13	INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN [DSS for transformation avenues]	JSI	Slovenia	RTD
14	META GROUP SRL [Innovation, Exploitation, Business briefs]	META	Italy	SME
15	UNIVERSITA POLITECNICA DELLE MARCHE [Participatory breeding, AURORA Farm]	UNIVPM	Italy	RTD
16	INSTITUT FÜR LEBENSMITTEL-UND UMWELTFORSCHUNG [Novel feed and non-food uses, AURORA Farm]	ILU	Germany	RTD
17	BIOFONTINHAS "THE ART OF BALANCE"[AURORA Farm]	BIOFO	Portugal	SME
18	SOCIEDADE AGRICOLA DO FREIXO DO MEIO Lda [AURORA Farm]	FDM	Portugal	SME
19	UNIV. DEGLI STUDI DI SCIENZE GASTRONOMICHE [Agroecological strategies, Ecosystem service, AURORA Farm]	UNISG	Italy	Higher Education
20	STOLZENBERGER REINER ERICH [Bakery, AURORA Farm]	SB	Germany	SME
21	CONNECTA NATURA [AURORA Farm]	CONAT	Spain	NGO
22	HIWEISS SRL [AURORA Farm]	HIW	Italy	SME
23	MITROPOULOS I. - LYRAS G. I.K.E. [AURORA Farm]	DIKOT	Greece	SME
24	INSTITUTE FOR AGROSTRATEGIES AND INNOVATIONS [AURORA Farm]	IAI	Bulgaria	NGO
25	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY [Economics and resilience]	WU	Netherlands	Higher Education
26	CENTRO RICERCHE PRODUZIONI ANIMALI [2 AURORA Farms]	CRPA	Italy	RTD
27	FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION OF THE UNITED NATIONS [Valorisation UC farmers, dissemination]	FAO	Italy	NGO
28	TECHNOLOGIKO PANEPISTIMIO KYPROU [AURORA Farm]	CUT	Cyprus	RTD